

WEB CHILD Working Papers, no. 1. 29-01-2026

A short introduction to searching in SolrWayback

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This guide was inspired by *Brugervejledning til Netarkivet* (The Royal Danish Library, 2024) and first made for the workshop Using the Archived Web as Research Data 20 March 2026 funded by AU Connect for a collaboration between the ERC Consolidator project Changing Childhoods in the Early Era of the WWW, WEBCHILD and the Royal Danish Library. WEBCHILD has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Seventh Framework Programme (FP7 2007-2013) (Grant agreement No. 101170060)

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18910538

Introduction

What is the archived web?

Websites shed light on many facets of modern human life and are an indispensable resource for contemporary history. They are constantly being uploaded, updated, and taken down again, making them an ephemeral resource for researchers. An effort to record this part of our shared heritage has been ongoing since 1996, when the Internet Archive started saving snapshots of “live” websites.

These archived pages are available to us today as archived web material, allowing researchers a glimpse into what the World Wide Web looked like in the past. Crucially, archived web material is an incomplete record. The archived web does not include all websites, their various versions, or every element contained within such websites. This means that many sites, and versions of sites that have existed in the past, were never archived. The extent of archiving also differs widely between websites: some sites have only been saved once or twice; others are saved hundreds of times per day. Working with archived Web material poses a unique challenge in source criticism, as questions regarding provenance are difficult to answer because not all websites explicitly state who authored them. On the other hand, these websites have allowed many voices from the past that would otherwise not have been heard to make it into the historical record.

Working with archived Web material is therefore an equally rewarding and challenging endeavor.

Recommended further reading: Niels Brügger, *The Archived Web. Doing History in the Digital Age*. MIT Press, 2018.

What is SolrWayback?

SolrWayback is an open-source software primarily developed by the Royal Danish Library. SolrWayback allows you to search and view archived Web material.

This is what SolrWayback looks like when opened initially:

SolrWayback, unlike most web archives, allows free-text searching. This means that you can search not only for URLs and website titles, but also in the main texts of the websites. This is advantageous because website URLs are often not known in advance.

In the search field you can use simple or complex searches. A simple search, such as “school”, yields thousands of results, even within a curated corpus:

For this reason, it is advantageous to limit the number of results. This can be done in two principal ways, either by constructing a more **complex search string** or by using the built-in **facets**.

Search strings

To get help with constructing a complex search string, click the question mark next to the search field:

This will open the search syntax guideline. The guide introduces the use of Boolean operators ('AND', 'OR', and 'NOT'), parentheses, wildcard searches, and more.

The following **Boolean operators** are supported in SolrWayback:

Operator	Example	Description
AND	computer AND apple	Both terms must match. Same as just: computer apple AND is the default operator between terms if not specified
OR	computer OR apple	Will match if just any of the terms is found
NOT	computer NOT apple	Must match computer but not apple. Alternative syntax: computer -apple

When combining Boolean operators, use **parentheses** to group terms together to avoid ambiguity.

In this example, SolrWayback returns results where either the word “school” or “kindergarten” is present along with the word “computer”:

Use the **wildcard operators** * and ? to get results with different spellings and endings.

Examples:

innovati* will match all words that starts with “innovati”, like innovation or innovative.

Analy?e will match both “analyse” and “analyze”.

Facets

Another way to narrow down your results is to use facets, found on the left side of the results list.

In the **Domain** facet you can choose to limit search results to a specific website:

FACETS

domain

- yahooligans.com (17,833)
- whitehouse.gov (9,637)
- kidlink.org (6,082)
- mercurycenter.com (5,450)
- lego.com (1,632)
- exploratorium.edu (1,255)
- eb.com (1,155)
- sportszone.com (927)
- kidpub.org (850)
- kidlink.dk (833)

[more domains](#)

Clicking on “whitehouse.gov” limits the results to pages from only that domain.

The same can be done with the facet **public_suffix**, which sorts results by the top level domain: .com, .gov, .edu, and so on.

The facet **crawl_year** limits results based on the year the websites were archived (crawled). Choosing “1997” limits the results to those webpages that were saved in 1997, but it does not guarantee that all

elements on a given webpage are from exactly 1997. The actual content of the website could, for instance, have been written in 1996 and not been updated since.

Archived web pages are sometimes collated, meaning that elements from different dates are displayed together as if they were from the same date. For instance, a website might have text from July and an image from March displayed together (imagine a newspaper page, but where the text, image, header, etc. are all from different dates, and where other pages in the same newspaper are from other dates too—this is what the archived web is mostly like). This temporal challenge is alleviated by the “View page resources” tool – see under the heading “Toolbar” below.

In short, archived web pages are sometimes collages with bits from different periods in times rather than photographs.

To remove a previously applied facet, click the cross button next to it:

The screenshot shows a search bar with the query "school* AND computer*". Below the search bar are options for "GROUPED SEARCH [?]", "IMAGE SEARCH [?]", and "URL SEARCH [?]". A navigation menu includes "SEARCH WITH UPLOADED FILE", "ABOUT THE COLLECTION", "NAVIGATION HISTORY" (with a red notification bubble containing the number 8), and "TOOLBOX". There is also a "GPS IMAGE SEARCH" option. Under the heading "APPLIED FACETS", the facet "crawl_year: 1997" is displayed with a small square button containing an 'X' next to it. A red circle highlights this button, and a red arrow points to it from the right. Below the facets, the "RESULTS" section shows "Showing 1 - 20 of 957 entries matching query." and a link for "See available export options".

Search strings and facets can be used together to sort results optimally. **However, you must always do the text box search first and apply the facets later, you cannot filter on facets and then do string search.** In the below example, all results from the website “kidlink.org” with either the word “kindergarten” or “school”, “schools”, “schooling”, etc. and the word “computer”, “computers”, etc. that were saved in 1997 are displayed:

The screenshot shows a search bar with the query "(school* OR kindergarten) AND computer*". Below the search bar are options for "GROUPED SEARCH [?]", "IMAGE SEARCH [?]", and "URL SEARCH [?]". A navigation menu includes "SEARCH WITH UPLOADED FILE", "ABOUT THE COLLECTION", "NAVIGATION HISTORY" (with a red notification bubble containing the number 13), and "TOOLBOX". There is also a "GPS IMAGE SEARCH" option. Under the heading "APPLIED FACETS", two facets are displayed: "crawl_year: 1997" and "domain: kidlink.org", each with a small square button containing an 'X' next to it. Below the facets, the "RESULTS" section shows "Showing 1 - 20 of 344 entries matching query." and a link for "See available export options". At the bottom, there are buttons for "Previous 20" and "Next 20", and a "Sort by: | score desc" dropdown menu.

Results

The results of your search are displayed in a list beneath the search field. Each result is displayed as a card with the website title, type, date it was saved, and URL. Below this metadata, an extract of the actual content of the website containing the terms searched for is displayed. If the website contains images, they are displayed beneath the text extract.

RESULTS

Showing 1 - 20 of 484,039 entries matching query. [see available export options](#)

Sort by:

 Yahooligans! #1
score: 33.78319

Type: html, web page @ yahooligans.com
Date: 07/06-2002
Url: <http://www.yahooligans.com:80/index.html>

Highlighted content:
"More... Around the [World Countries](#), [U.S. States](#), [Holidays](#)... [School Bell Lang](#)."

Images: showing 4 out of 10

SEARCH FOR IMAGE
PAGES LINKING TO IMAGE
[HTTP://US.11.YIMG.COM/US.YIMG.COM/1/LIGANS/FP/ASKEARL.GIF](http://us.11.yimg.com/us.yimg.com/1/ligans/fp/askearl.gif)

HELLO...

If you click the title of the card (in this example, **Yahooligans!**), you are taken directly to the archived webpage in a new browser window. Here you can see what the website looked like when it was archived, if the complete site was saved (but remember that at the time it was live, it was viewed in a different browser, perhaps on a screen that was very different from yours). If all page elements were not saved in their entity, what you see is the web archives collation:

YAHOO! LIGANS!
the Web Guide for Kids

Friday June 7, 2002

- Games
- Movies
- Jokes
- Science
- Reference
- Ask Earl
- News
- Sports
- Astrology
- Messenger
- Shout Out
- Parents' Guide
- Cool Sites
- Teachers' Guide

Yahooligans! News
2002 World Cup - Associated Press
England's David Beckham celebrates following his team's victory over Argentina in the 2002 World Cup Group F soccer match between England and Argentina. [More...](#)

Search

Yahooligans Directory

- Around the World**
Countries, U.S. States, Holidays...
- School Bell**
Lang. Arts, Math, Social Studies...
- Arts & Entertainment**
TV, Movies, Jokes, Music...
- Science & Nature**
Space, Animals, Dinosaurs...
- Computers & Games**
Games, Screensavers, World Wide Web...
- Sports & Recreation**
Baseball, Basketball, Outdoors...

Yahooligans! Games
[Play Now!](#)
Chess, checkers, tic tac toe, dominoes, and lots of other cool games. [Learn more.](#)

Joke of the Day
What did the duck say when the waitress came?
Answer!

Ask Earl
How far does a soccer player run in an average...
Answer!

Help!

International Yahooligans! - [Japan](#) and [Korea](#)
Make Yahoo! your Homepage - [Terms of Service](#) - [Suggest a Site](#)

Toolbar

When you open an archived webpage you will find the “Toolbar” (in blue) at the upper-left corner of your browser window, right below your bookmarks:

Clicking this opens the toolbar menu as an overlay on top of the webpage:

The toolbar displays information about the webpage, including the exact time it was archived (harvested) and the URL.

If you click the “**Harvest calendar**” button in the toolbar, a new window will open displaying information on when and how often the webpage has been saved:

If you click the “**View page resources**” button in the toolbar, a new window will open displaying information on the different elements of the webpage and if any elements are missing.

As noted above, the website as presented in web archives is sometimes a collage rather than a snapshot, and this page tells you the time difference between the different elements:

MAXIMUM TIME DIFFERENCE FOR RESSOURCES

Backward ← 16 days
 Forward → 61 days

MISSING RESOURCES

1. http://us.news1.yimg.com/us.yimg.com/p/ap/20020607/thumb.1023465333.wcup_gbr_xen_arg_soc_wcspo167.jpg

In this example, we note that the oldest element on the webpage is 16 days older than the archiving time, and the most recent element was added 61 days after the archiving time.

WEB CHILD

Below, the elements that were collated on the webpage as it appears are listed along with their time difference. A negative time difference means it is older than the webpage save time, and a positive number means it is more recent:

RESOURCE URL	CONTENT TYPE	TIME DIFFERENCE	SEE/DOWNLO

